

Original Research Article

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of infection control guidelines among dental students in Islamic International Dental Hospital Islamabad, Pakistan

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Abstract

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The aim of the study was to investigate the knowledge, attitude and practice among 3rd year and final year students at Islamic International Dental Hospital, Riphah International University, Islamabad. This study consisted of 151 students of 3rd year and final year. Questionnaire was containing 21 questions related to vaccination status, barrier techniques infection control practices and awareness. The questionnaire was distributed through Google forms to the students after taking consent from them. The data was analyzed and tabulated through SPSS version 23. All of the participants responded to the questionnaire (response rate =100%). The compliance for the hepatitis B vaccination was slightly low in the students' (79.9%), however compliance with the use of protective barriers was high with the exception of protective eye wear which was only 23.8% . the score for knowledge, attitude and practice of 3rd year students was higher than final year students. The result of this study was not very satisfactory. More knowledge about infection control measures should be provided to the students, moreover efforts are needed to improve the attitude and practice of the dental students towards infection control at Islamic International Dental Hospital, Islamabad. Further education may be appropriate in number of areas such as wearing protective eye wear and vaccination against Hepatitis B.

Keyword: Cross infection, Dental students, Infection control

INTRODUCTION

Dental procedures are associated with risk of exposure to blood and transmission of blood –borne diseases can occur easily in the dental clinical environment (Mohiuddin and Dawani, 2015). Dental health care practitioners (DHCPs) are more prone to infections. They are infected by pathogens that directly enter host's body. Another route of transmission of these disease causing agents are in the form of droplets either blood, serum or air borne. (Harrel and Molinari, 2004; Mohiuddin and Dawani, 2015; Mousa et al., 1997; Taiwo and Aderinokun, 2002). Thus it is essential for DHCPs to use

all protective means such as wearing gloves, face –mask, eyewear as well as use an adequate high speed suction while using high and low speed rotary instruments (Mohiuddin and Dawani, 2015).

DHCPs are potentially more at risk of infections caused by wide variety of causative organisms namely mycobacterium tuberculosis, hepatitis B and C virus, streptococci, staphylococci, herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV 1), mumps, rubella, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), influenza (Mohiuddin and Dawani, 2015). Cross infection prevention in dental clinic and schools

during a dental procedure is of immense significance, as all para-dental auxiliaries must adhere to the standard guidelines of prevention and safety measures particularly at the time of patient handling (Assiri et al., 2018).

The guidelines related to infection control measures in dental setup, have been updated and made available by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) in 2003. The main aim of these guidelines is to provide a working environment with all standard safety measures along with prevention of transmitting potential pathogens and nosocomial infections among dentists, DHCPs and their patients (Askarian and Asadian, 2009). According to these guiding principles of CDC, it is mandatory to wear face-masks and gloves during each and every patient followed by changing face- masks and gloves after completion of dental procedures on a patient. Furthermore, CDC's guidelines also recommend to wear protective eye cover and properly disinfect clothes before re-use. Moreover, after performing chair- side dental treatments, hands must be thoroughly washed with anti-septic solution (Harte, 2004; Kohn et al., 2003).

Dental schools are responsible for providing appropriate infection control measures, proper training of dental students to protect patients, and for the establishment of safer work conditions (de Souza et al., 2006). In 2003, the Center for Disease Control and Prevention of the United States of America updated its guidelines on infection control in dental settings. (Kohn et al., 2003)

Awareness and compliance with these recommendations are crucial for the prevention of occupational and nosocomial infections in healthcare workers, including dental healthcare professionals. Unfortunately, despite the considerable emphasis placed on standardized infection control procedures, it appears that only a few dentists adhered to these protocols in their dental practice (Askarian and Asadian, 2009; Jain et al., 2010; Yüzbasıoglu et al., 2009)

Dental education can play a significant role in the training of dentists by helping them to adopt adequate knowledge and attitudes related to infection control procedures. The purpose of the study, therefore, was to investigate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding infection control measures among dental students in Islamic international dental hospital, Islamabad.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects and sampling

It was a cross sectional study which was conducted among 3rd year and final year dental students of Islamic International Dental College, Riphah International University Islamabad. A total of 150 students were included in the study. The questionnaire was planned to

obtain information about infection control knowledge, attitude and practice among the dental students. The research proposal was approved by the ethical committee of the university before the study. Infection control measures and awareness were provided to the students in all the four years of their BDS program.

The survey was conducted between 30th July 2020 and 6th August 2020. The questionnaire was uploaded on student's moelim lds. It was compulsory for all the students to fill the questionnaire. In the study survey no personal information was captured. In addition, confidentiality of the participants was maintained throughout the study.

Questionnaire design

The questionnaire was taken from the study that was conducted in Dr. Ishrat-ul-Ebad Khan Institute of Oral Health Sciences, a public setup of Karachi, Pakistan. This study consisted of 21 questions which were divided into 4 sections. 3 questions were related to demographic information like age, gender and participant's designation. 2 questions were asked to assess their knowledge, 10 questions to assess attitude and 6 questions to judge infection control practice. Knowledge, attitude and practice of infection control was assessed at three possible levels (yes, no and may be).

Statistical analysis

The questionnaire data was entered in spss version 23. For knowledge, attitude and practice, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation was calculated

RESULTS

In this questionnaire based cross sectional study undergraduate students took part in the study. The questionnaire was distributed to 151 dental students from 3rd year and final year, of which all of them responded (response rate =100%). 92.1 participants were present in the age group 21-25 whereas 7.9% were in age group 16-20. Out of 151 participants 80.1% were females and 19.9% were males. Table 1, Figure 1

Knowledge

88.3% (n=68) of 3rd year and 86.1% (n=63) of the final year students take detailed medical history. Vaccinated students for hepatitis B were 83.1% and 75.6% for 3rd year and final year students respectively, which is a

Table 1. Shows demographics of third year and final year students.

Variables			Frequency (%)
Age			
≥	20	years	12 (7.9)
<	20	years	139 (92.1)
Designation			
Students in 3 rd Year			77 (51)
Students in Final Year			74 (49)

Figure 2. Shows percentages of 3rd year students**Table 2.** Shows infection control Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of the study population

Variables	Frequency (%)combined	3 rd Year	Final Year
Knowledge			
Take detailed medical history	131 (86.8)	69 (88.3)	63 (86.1)
vaccinated against Hepatitis B	120 (79.5)	64 (83.1)	56 (75.6)
Attitude			
Wear Gloves Before Touching Anything in The Department	87 (57.6)	49 (63.6)	38 (51.3)
Change Gloves after every patient	151 (100)	77 (100)	74 (100)
Wear Face Mask in the Department	119 (78.8)	63 (81.8)	56 (75.6)
Change Facemask in between The Patients	87 (57.6)	44 (57.1)	43 (58.1)
Wear Protective Eye wear	36 (23.8)	25 (32.4)	11 (14.9)
Disinfect Impressions after making them	134 (88.7)	65 (84.4)	69 (93.2)
Change Hand piece between patients	120 (79.5)	62 (80.5)	58 (78.3)
Change Extraction instruments after every patient	147 (97.4)	74 (96.1)	73 (98.6)
Change saliva ejector after every patient	136 (90.1)	66 (85.7)	70 (94.5)
Change Burs in operative Dentistry after every patient	140(82.7)	68 (88.3)	72 (97.2)
Practices			
Wash Hands before and after treatments	135 (89.4)	71 (92.2)	64 (82.4)
Wear hand jewelry or wrist watch during treatment	39 (25.8)	17 (22)	22 (29)
Use rubber dam	50 (33.1)	25 (32.4)	25 (33.7)
Use autoclave for sterilization of instruments	150 (99.3)	77 (100)	73 (98.6)
Use plastic wrappings for sterilized instruments	130 (86.1)	69 (89.6)	61 (82.4)
Does your department use special containers for disposal of sharp objects	122 (80.8)	58 (75.3)	64 (86.4)

Table 3. Show correlation among Knowledge, Attitude and Practice score.

Variables	Correlation-co-efficient	P-value
Knowledge-Attitude	0.48	0.56
Attitude-Practice	0.437	0
Knowledge-Practice	0.4	0.626

common infection in a dental setup. The vaccination rate was also higher among females (82.6%) than males (66.6%).

Attitude

Nearly, all of the 3rd year and final year students mentioned changing gloves after every patient, but before touching anything in the department from 3rd year 63.6% (n=49) and from final year only 51.3% (n=38) students wear gloves. About wearing masks 81.8% (n=63) of 3rd year and 75.6% (n=56) of the final year wear masks and only 57.1% and 58.1% students from 3rd year and final year change masks after every patient, whereas only 32.4% (n=25) from the 3rd year and 14.8% (n=11) from the final year students mentioned to wear protective eyewear. On inquiring about disinfection of impression 84.4% (n=65) from 3rd year and 93.2% (n=69) from final year reported affirmatively, 80.5% (n=62) and 78.3% (n=58) of 3rd year and final year stated that they change handpiece after every patient. Regarding changing extraction instruments and saliva ejector 96.1% (n=74) and 85.7% (n=66) from 3rd year and 98.6% (n=73) and 94.5% (n=70) respectively. Furthermore, 88.3% and 97.2% from 3rd year and final year students stated that they do change handpiece burs during operative dentistry procedures after every patient.

Practice

Regarding dental practices of the study participant's majority of the students washed hands before and after the dental procedure, 92.2% from 3rd year and 82.4% from final year. Only a few participants from 3rd year 22% (n=17) and final year 29% (n=22) hand jewelry and wrist watches during treatment. Questions related to use of an autoclave for sterilization of handpieces, plastic wrappings for sterilized instruments and special containers for the disposal of sharp instruments; 100%, 89.6% and 75.3% of 3rd year and 98.6%, 82.4% and 86.4% of final year responded positive. 32.4% (n=25) and 33.7% (n=25) from 3rd and final year reported that they also use rubber dam application.

DISCUSSION

Infection control is a vital discipline which never remains

constant. In health care settings in order to avoid the chance of receiving vocational diseases from either known or unknown sources standard isolation precautions are composed. Recognition and acceptance with these suggestions are decisive for the obstruction of infections between health care workers, containing dental health care professionals. Health care professionals are the most susceptible for irresistible sicknesses in workplaces (Askarian and Asadian, 2009). Dental practitioners are over and over presented to numerous microorganisms present in saliva and blood as result, rate of specific illnesses is high among them when contrasted with general population (Acosta-Gío et al., 2008). It is significant for any hospital or dental clinic to frame-up its own steps to avoid the increase in infectious and contagious diseases. So it is very necessary for dental health care professionals to be acquainted with the risks and solemnity of infections. This survey was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of dental students regarding infection control procedures in Islamic International Dental Hospital, Islamabad.

Transmission of microorganisms through the spray of dental handpieces can likewise be considered an airborne or waterborne means of emanation, which may influence both the patient and the dental group. (Laheij et al., 2012) Although the number of bacteria in dental rooms are not fundamentally higher than bacterial counts in open regions including public areas, the danger of transmission may be higher in dental facility contrasted with an open zone because of the kind of microorganisms, having exposure time and host susceptibility (Kimmerle et al., 2012).

Hepatitis B vaccination among dentists ranges from 6% to 95% but during the past few years it has increased (Gershon et al., 1998). The findings of our study showed that 83.1% and 75.6% among 3rd year and final year students were vaccinated against Hepatitis B. Moreover, female students completed the vaccination more often than male students. This finding may be due to women being more concerned about protective measures. This finding is much higher than the study conducted in Yemen and India who found that 70.7% and 38% of students were vaccinated against hepatitis B (Halboub et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2011), this rate is much lower than the studies done in Canada (100%), Brazil (90.8%) and UAE (95.8%) (Rahman et al., 2013). Vaccination cost and lack of knowledge about the significance of immunization among dental students might also be a major factor about the decrease in immunization of hepatitis B.

Regardless of the certainty that there is verification of

development in consent with barrier use in many countries, still there is a need to upgrade the devotion of dentists for both infection control regulations and standard precautions. In the present study the acquiescence of the students of 3rd and final year who wear gloves and change gloves after every patient was high, similar to the other studies done in UK, Iran, Canada, Brazil and UAE (Rahman et al., 2013). The use of gloves in the study conducted in Abha was 99.5% (Assiri et al., 2018). The prevalence of wearing face masks and protective eyewear was not very satisfactory. It was only 75.6% and 32.2%. This was also similar to the study lead in Abha (Assiri et al., 2018) and other countries (Arias et al., 2016). Students should be reminded that disregarding the utilization of protective eyewear may put them in danger of transmission of infectious diseases through the uncovered films. The aftereffects of this investigation exhibit a need to additionally emphasize eye protection. The significance of defensive eyewear was seen as in light of a legitimate concern for both dental specialists and patients because of the dangers related with floating debris and aerosols. The utilization of eye protections with side shields and ordinary checking of its basic respectability, diminishes the danger of conjunctivitis, eye harm or even total loss of vision. Masks ought to be changed when they become tainted, wet or more often, for example when appointments are long (Honkala et al., 2002), but the result of our study showed that only 57.1 % students change masks after every appointment. Though this rate is higher than the survey done by R. Varshan whose values were only 16.1% (Pearson et al., 2015), still more knowledge should be given to the students. Hand cleanliness is viewed as the absolute best strategy for the avoidance and control of healthcare related infections (Mutters et al., 2014). Compliance with hand cleanliness methods is fundamental as the hands of health care workers may provide a pool for some microorganisms (Mutters et al., 2014). Hand hygiene habits are good among all the students. For 3rd year students it was 92.2% and for final year students it was 82.4%. This finding is higher the studies done by Rashman et al. (47.9%) (Rahman et al., 2013) and Amorim-Finzi (45%) (de Amorim-Finzi et al., 2010). Our findings should be 100% because hand hygiene is very important. Strict measures should be taken to remind the students about hand washing. Hand washing signs can be placed near each basin in dental hospitals as it is a significant element. All students (n=151) in our study used autoclave to sterilize their instruments. Henrique et al. (2009) done a ten-year study to evaluate mentalities and conduct of dental students concerning disease control rules. In 1995, most students utilized an autoclave to clean instruments (83.8%), and this rate expanded in 2005 (95.9%).

The scores of 3rd year students were more as compared to final year students this noteworthy scores of

information and consistency could be because in this field it is their first clinical year where the basic knowledge about infection control is overemphasized on both hypothetical and functional levels. Overall knowledge and practice of infection control measures was not very satisfactory among dental students. The attitude towards infection control measures was good, yet a more prominent consistency was required. The findings of our study should alarm dental instructors about the significance of teaching their students clearly and extensively about disease control measures. It is the moral commitment of each health care worker to defend themselves and their patients from cross-contamination. Because the network expects zero danger of disease transmission from health care workers, a novel, more compelling methodology is expected to raise the attention to the significance of vaccination coverage, protective eyewear, and adherence to contamination control protocols.

LIMITATIONS

There are a few limitations of the study, firstly, the responses were based on students' self- assessment rather than being given under the oversight of the supervisors in the clinical situation. In this manner, the reactions probably won't have precisely mirrored the genuine degrees of knowledge, attitude and practice. Therefore, the detailed degree of training may be lower than the genuine level. Secondly, these number of questions cannot show the genuine knowledge and practice of the respondents.

CONCLUSION

In general, our study showed not very satisfactory compliance with the advocated infection control practices among dental students of Islamic International Dental Hospital. The difference between knowledge and attitude could be due to insufficient supply of personal protective equipment, improper disposal of sharp objects, carelessness and lack of educational programs. It is important to adequately speak with students about related dangers and significance of transmission of infection diseases and manifestation during dental treatments. With all infection control conventions previously actualized in dental schools, the test stays on improving consistence with disease control recommendations.

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